

Chemical Examination of *Cuscuta Reflexa*, Roxb.

Part II. The Constitution of Cuscutalin.

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In a previous communication Agarwal and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 384) in the course of their investigations on the chemical constituents of *Cuscuta reflexa*, Roxb. (Syn. Amerbel) of the Natural Order *Convulvulaceae*, isolated from it a white crystalline substance of the nature of a lactone called by them cuscutalin (about 1.5%). In the present paper it is proposed to throw some light on the chemical constitution of the aforesaid cuscutalin.

The elementary analysis and the molecular weight determination established the formula $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$. Out of the four oxygen atoms one is present as a phenolic hydroxy group, since it forms a monoacetyl and a monocarbethoxy derivative. It also gave a light red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, but no precipitate with lead acetate, silver nitrate or mercuric chloride.

Although containing no aldehydic or ketonic groups, since it does not react with hydroxylamine, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, nor reduces Fehling's solution, cuscutalin reduces Tollen's reagent gradually. An alcoholic solution of cuscutalin could also be slowly titrated with alkalis. It dissolves in alcoholic caustic potash on warming with a beautiful yellow colouration and gives a reddish brown colour with alkaline potassium nitroprusside. These reactions place it beyond doubt into the group of $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ -unsaturated lactones which were first of all studied by Thiele (*Annalen*, 1901, 319, 155) and more exhaustively by Jacobs and collaborators (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1926, 67, 333; *Phys. Rev.*, 1933, 13, 222). Jacobs (*loc. cit.*) got so uniform results with all the $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ - and $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -lactones in the light of the reactions enumerated by Thiele (*loc. cit.*) that there appears to be complete justification in considering this substance to be $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ -unsaturated lactone. From some of the Indian medicinal plants also, substances of the nature of lactone have been isolated and they have without fail given all the reactions of Thiele (*loc. cit.*). Sen (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 651) isolated corchoritin from jute seeds, Dikshit and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 759) marmelosin from *Aegle marmelos* and Agarwal and Dutt (*Current Science*, 1934, 3, 250; *Proc. Acad. Sci.*

U. P., 1935, 3, 250) α -elaterin from *Citrullus colocynthis* which were all unsaturated lactones and gave reactions described above. Thus out of the four oxygen atoms, three have been accounted for, one in the hydroxy group and two in the lactonic grouping. On complete methylation with methyl sulphate after first saponifying the lactone with caustic potash, a dimethoxymonomethyl ester was obtained. This was evidently due to the breaking of the lactone by saponification and subsequent methylation.

Cuscutalin is unsaturated. It decolourises bromine water slowly and bromine in chloroform readily. It also decolourises an alkaline solution of potassium permanganate quite easily. On treatment with bromine in chloroform a dibromo-bromide was obtained, containing three atoms of bromine and also one unsaturated linkage. It could also be reduced by zinc dust and acetic acid to give a dihydro derivative. Volumetric estimation of unsaturation in the usual manner established the presence of two double bonds in the molecule. The tetrabromo derivative could not be prepared in a crystalline state.

Cuscutalin being a hydroxy lactone was easily acted upon by concentrated hydrochloric acid to form anhydrocuscutalin. By this reaction the hydroxy group was lost since anhydrocuscutalin gave no acetyl derivative.

Cuscutalin dissolves in boiling alcoholic potash with frothing and on acidification liberated the lactone of another isomeric acid melting at 103° and possessing the same empirical formula as cuscutalin. The acid could not be isolated as such. Cuscutalin is optically active and in chloroform gave a small *dextro* rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{27} = +8^\circ$.

On fusion with caustic potash cuscutalin gave formic acid, cinnamic acid and an aromatic unsaturated hydrocarbon, (m.p. 82°), which could not be identified. On oxidation with a 3% alkaline solution of potassium permanganate, oxalic acid and benzaldehyde were detected. The formation of benzaldehyde may be due to the oxidation of cinnamic acid which might have been formed as an intermediate product. On heating carefully by itself in a dry tube, cuscutalin first melts, then carbonises and partially sublimes unchanged. A small amount of the anhydrocuscutalin was also detected along with some unidentified hydrocarbons in the process of dry distillation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The crude cuscutalin ($C_{18}H_{10}O_4$) can be crystallised first from methyl alcohol which leaves a brown waxy matter, and finally from

ethyl alcohol whereby colourless flakes of cuscotalin are obtained melting sharp at 68°.

Monoacetylcuscotalin.—1 G of cuscotalin was refluxed on a sand-bath with excess of acetic anhydride (25 c. c.) and fused sodium acetate for about 2 hours. An oil separated which solidified to a greyish white amorphous mass on pouring the mixture into water. It was collected, dried and dissolved in hot methyl alcohol. A portion (m.p. 60-62°) remained undissolved and the methyl alcoholic solution on concentration and standing deposited the acetyl derivative in fine colourless plates, m.p. 74°. (Found: C, 72·0; H, 3·9. $C_{20}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 72·3; H, 3·6 per cent).

Monocarbethoxy-cuscotalin.—Ethyl chloroformate was added drop by drop till in excess to 1 g. of cuscotalin suspended in pyridine. The mixture was then rapidly shaken whereby a pink coloured solution was obtained. After about half an hour of vigorous shaking the solution was poured into water when it separated in thin colourless form. It was kept overnight, filtered and dried. The crude product melted at 80° but on crystallisation from alcohol, from which colourless flakes were obtained, it melted at 105°. (Found: C, 70·0; H, 4·1. $C_{21}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 69·6; H, 3·8 per cent).

Dimethoxycuscotalin monomethyl ester.—Cuscotalin (0·8 g.) was saponified by warming with caustic potash (10 %, 25 c.c.) and the yellow solution treated drop by drop with the theoretical quantity of dimethylsulphate with vigorous shaking. After about 4 hours of shaking the ester separated as an oil on the top, which on keeping with water overnight solidified. This was collected, powdered and crystallised from ethyl alcohol as white microcrystalline substance, m.p. 78°. (Found: C, 71·4; H, 5·2. $C_{21}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 71·99; H, 5·14 per cent).

Anhydrocuscotalin.—Cuscotalin (1 g.) was dissolved by slight warming in concentrated hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1·19, 25 c.c.) and the light yellow solution was then heated for about half an hour. Some crystalline suspension began to separate and on cooling the solution the anhydro derivative separated in an amorphous form. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water until free from acid and finally dried over caustic potash. The vitreous mass was then crystallised from hot ethyl alcohol as fine colourless needles, m.p. 71-72°. (Found: C, 79·1; H, 3·00. $C_{18}H_8O_3$ requires C, 79·41; H, 2·94 per cent).

Dibromocuscotalin bromide.—Cuscotalin (1.3 g.) dissolved in chloroform (100 c.c.) was treated with an excess of bromine (3 c.c.) dissolved in chloroform. The mixture was placed in a dark place for some time. It was then refluxed over a water-bath, when fumes of hydrogen bromide were given off. The excess of bromine and chloroform were then removed and the product on being dried over quicklime for about a week solidified to a dark coloured amorphous mass. It was finally crystallised from dilute acetic acid as pale brownish yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 64°. (Found: Br, 45.1. $C_{18}H_9O_4 Br_3$ requires Br, 45.36 per cent).

The volumetric estimation of unsaturation in cuscotalin (0.43 g.) dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (10 c.c.) was carried out in the usual way. It showed two double bonds in the molecule.

Dihydrocuscotalin.—Cuscotalin (1 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) and the solution treated with zinc dust (10 g.) in small quantities. When the reaction was complete, the mixture was filtered hot into a large volume of cold water. The reduced product separated as a fine colourless precipitate, which was crystallised from alcohol in fine white flakes, m.p. 91°. (Found: C, 73.69; H, 4.50. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.99; H, 4.11 per cent).

Neutralisation value of cuscotalin.—Titration of cuscotalin with standard alkali was possible and the neutralisation value was found to be 17.8, the neutralisation equivalent is 266. The *saponification value of cuscotalin*, determined in the usual manner, was 321.8 and the saponification equivalent 173.9.

Action of alcoholic potash on cuscotalin.—Cuscotalin (5 g.) was saponified by boiling with 0.1 N-alcoholic potash. When the saponification was complete the brilliant yellow solution was cooled and the alcohol removed. The mass was then acidified with acetic acid, when a voluminous flocculent mass separated, which was collected and crystallised from alcohol as colourless scales, m.p. 102°. It dissolved in ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol and acetic acid slowly. It developed a pinkish red colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid on warming. (Found: C, 74.1; H, 3.9. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.5; H, 3.4 per cent).

Caustic potash fusion of cuscotalin.—Cuscotalin (5 g.) was heated with solid caustic potash (50 g.) moistened with a little water (5 c.c.) in a nickel crucible at 140-150° for about 2 hours and then at 180° for 1 hour. The melt boiled with considerable frothing at first and the smell of formic acid was evolved. The dirty white melt was

cooled and lixiviated with water when a white substance remained undissolved. The solution was concentrated, acidified with a little hydrochloric acid and extracted repeatedly with ether, the ether removed when an acid was obtained as fine shining needles, m.p. 182°. It was partly soluble in water, insoluble in petroleum ether and could be crystallised from alcohol in large needles. It gave a very faint colour with ferric chloride. A dilute solution of potassium permanganate and bromine water were decolourised. The analysis of its lead salt gave, taking it to be monobasic, M.W. 142. This was identified to be cinnamic acid. The mother liquor on examination gave tests for formic acid.

The alkali-insoluble portion was dried and refluxed with methyl alcohol, when a portion, greyish white in appearance (m.p. 64°), remained undissolved. The soluble portion on cooling deposited colourless flakes, m.p. 80-84°, suspected to be some aromatic unsaturated hydrocarbon. A solution of potassium permanganate and bromine water were decolourised; concentrated sulphuric acid had no reaction. The yield obtained was too poor to admit of any detailed investigation.

Oxidation of cuscutalin with potassium permanganate.—Cuscutalin (3 g.) in dilute caustic soda solution was treated on the water-bath with an aqueous solution of potassium permanganate (3%) in a big porcelain basin; smell of benzaldehyde was detected in the process of oxidation. The solution of permanganate was decolourised and manganese dioxide was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to a small volume. On acidification and extraction with ether traces of oxalic acid were detected and confirmed by preparation of the calcium salt.

Action of heat on cuscutalin.—Cuscutalin (3 g.) was very gradually heated in a small distilling flask. It first melted to a colourless liquid which gradually became brown and evolved white fumes which were collected in a test tube containing a little water. A small quantity of unidentifiable products was obtained. From the sides of the flask a substance was obtained, m.p. 71-72°, which was identified as anhydrocuscutalin. No other product could be separated.

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